

D3.4 2nd OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

RDA	Research Data Alliance
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
RDA-MP	Research Data Alliance Maintenance Platform
RDA TIGER	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

This report is intended to update and extend the ground covered by the earlier RDA TIGER WP3 deliverable D3.1, submitted in June 2023. It does not reproduce content from that earlier overview but attempts to provide a summary of relevant activity occurring in the last 15 months and its relationship to the RDA ecosystem. In doing so, the primary purpose of this document is to support the landscape research activities within WP3 as well as the other services of the project, as follows:

- Facilitation of the Working Groups' internal processes (WP5), by documenting and summarising the changes in the landscape;
- Communication support (WP2), by identifying stakeholders that could have a particularly keen interest in the outputs of the supported Working Group;
- Output support (WP4), by gathering information related to organisation and external publications that can be included in the Maintenance Platform once the technical developments have been completed.

More broadly, we also hope that the document is helpful to anyone interested in the recent developments in EOSC- and FAIR data-related activities. To support this broader use, the document provides extensive links to the background material, primarily as footnotes to make it as easy as possible to access the background material with minimal disruption of the reading (or browsing) process of the document itself.

Building upon D3.1 content, we provide an update on the progress to date with preparing the contents of the RDA graph database, its impact on RDA TIGER activity, and how it contributes to the OS landscape work that informs the landscape awareness service. We also analyse the themes and topics that appear to be developing amongst recent global Open Science initiatives and activities, and the extent to which these are reflected in the nascent and emerging RDA Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER support services. We also offer some observations on apparent gaps in provision of RDA Working Groups that tackle contemporary Open Science issues as mapped i) against the current EOSC SRIA aims, and ii) geographically.

However, we do not attempt to perform advanced analysis of the observed developments for two reasons:

- The Maintenance Platform will provide tools to directly support many of the analysis tasks, both statistical ones (e.g., number of publications per year, languages used) and network analysis (co-authorship, topics of interest, institutions,...).
- The impact of any particular development is highly dependent on the focus of the Working Group supported and the extent of its progress.

Nevertheless, we observed a few common trends that are relevant for the project as a whole, as well as for the future support activities that will eventually supersede the role RDA TIGER is currently playing. The first such observation is the relatively rapid increase in the number of RDA WGs, from 47 in June 2023 to 59 in October 2024, with further seven waiting for endorsement. In parallel with this increase, the proportion of WGs focused on domain specific issues has grown. These trends should be seen both as an asset (growing

community with greater diversity leading to new cross-pollination opportunities) and a challenge (renewed efforts as well as new tools and approaches to maintain a coherent overview of the activities are needed). Furthermore, additional efforts are needed to balance the participation across geographical areas and language groups. Successfully addressing these challenges will mean that the RDA and the RDA TIGER project could be even more efficient and effective in supporting alignment of EOSC and other European FAIR-data related initiatives with global developments.

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1. Introduction and context

The RDA TIGER Landscape Analysis Service, as one branch of the overall RDA TIGER WG support service, aims to support the development of Working Groups (WGs) within the Research Data Alliance (RDA) by providing background knowledge of Open Science activities to avoid duplication and ensure that emerging WGs are well-positioned to address current research and data challenges.

In principle, the Landscape Analysis Service does not engage with the supported RDA WGs directly. Instead, it supports the facilitators in their role as the primary support contact point with the WGs and their co-chairs. In addition to providing targeted support for the WGs based on the requests from the facilitators, the Landscape Analysis Service will collect resources and annotations that can contribute to the RDA Knowledge Graph (part of the Maintenance Platform/Output Support service provided by WP4).

This report is intended¹ to update and extend the ground covered by the earlier RDA TIGER WP3 deliverable D3.1², submitted in June 2023 and briefly summarised in the following section 2 below. Building upon D3.1 content, we provide an update on the progress to date with building the RDA graph database, its impact on RDA TIGER activity, and how it contributes to the OS landscape work that informs the Landscape Analysis Service. We also analyse the themes and topics that appear to be developing and the extent to which these are reflected in current WG submissions.

1.1. Relevance and added value to EOSC ecosystem

The RDA TIGER support project exists to facilitate and support RDA WGs with a specific focus on those WGs that can strengthen the links between key European and international initiatives, resulting in concrete alignment, harmonisation, and standardisation of Open Science developments and technologies globally. In this way, the project will directly contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by supporting, via the WGs, the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs relating to EOSC and European Open Science developments more generally. The role of the Landscape Analysis Service is to provide all the project activities with a coherent high-level stakeholder map that helps to optimise project's activities, especially ones around facilitation, engagement and communication.

Looking specifically at the latest set of Implementation Challenges in the EOSC SRIA³, we can gauge the extent to which RDA WGs are providing coverage of these priority topics, as follows.

- Implementation Challenge: Identifiers

¹ D3.4 description from the project Description of Work: "Second iteration of OS landscape study, updating on existing OS initiatives and highlighting new developments in areas aligning with potential WGs."

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

³ i.e. Version 1.2, available at

https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

- RDA TIGER supported the National PID Strategies WG that created the “RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist”, which fosters the development of national PID strategies by providing a comparison guide and a checklist.
- Implementation Challenge: Metadata and Ontologies
 - The work of several TIGER WGs directly addresses the priorities identified under this challenge.
 - The FAIR Mappings WG defines approaches to FAIR mappings/crosswalks.
 - Provision and stimulation of uptake of FAIR terminologies, ontologies, metadata and coordinate work on metadata and ontologies is addressed by the following groups: Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG, Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in SSH WG, Wind Energy Community Standards WG, Creating a Multi-omics Metadata Schema Standard Reporting Matrix WG.
- Implementation Challenge: FAIR Metrics and Certification
 - The RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Adoption and Outreach WG works with repositories and certification standards and schema providers to develop use cases of TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories adoption, and map TRUST to different standards and schemas.
 - The Community- based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) addresses a need in the community of data repositories and associated services worldwide: namely, how to extend the umbrella of trust, as exemplified by formal certification authorities such as ISO and CoreTrustSeal, to a wider range of service providers on which many repositories are dependent.
- Implementation Challenge: EOSC Interoperability Framework
 - RDA TIGER addresses the gaps ‘Support for standards development and adoption’ and ‘Engagement with research communities’.

In the day-to-day support effort for these WGs, the project aims to effectively identify key partners for the groups, increasing their work efficiency by facilitation and other support actions in order to ultimately maximise the impact WG results have on the EOSC, global Open Science, and society.

2. Summary of D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets

RDA TIGER D3.1, ‘OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets’, provided an initial overview of the Open Science landscape at an early stage of the RDA TIGER project (June 2023). It attempted to lay out some of the main lenses or views upon current Open Science activity in order to produce a substantial and useful overview of projects and initiatives but also one with an appropriate focus for the context of situating new RDA WGs.

We designed the approach to analysis based upon what was likely to be useful to anyone proposing or conceptualising a new RDA WG in practice. A WG must serve a clearly defined community within the Open Science landscape. Any community developed within

the Open Science ecosystem is most likely to converge around a domain-agnostic research process, tool, method or data type; or around a particular domain. D3.1 therefore provided a domain-agnostic and also a domain-specific overview of initiatives, groups and projects arising with the global networks of RDA TIGER partners.

In addition, another 'lens' or view likely to be used when surveying the global Open Science landscape is to consider geographically-bound networks or communities of practice. There are significant numbers of nationally and regionally-funded initiatives and projects in the Open Science landscape so these were also compiled.

In this way, current Open Science initiatives were analysed in D3.1 primarily by their relationship to *domain-agnostic* activity, *domain-specific* research or *geographically-bound* initiatives. The first of these categories in D3.1 included domain-agnostic RDA Working Groups and Interest Groups, RDA outputs and recommendations, and RDA pathways; EOSC activities including EOSC-funded projects, EOSC SRIA and EOSC Task Forces; domain-agnostic CODATA task groups, CODATA Working Groups, the Global Open Science Cloud initiative; the WorldFAIR project and its cross-domain activities; the Global Open Research Commons typology of elements; the Research Software Alliance task forces; and various relevant advisory organisations.

Domain-specific initiatives in D3.1 included the RDA Working Groups, RDA Interest Groups, RDA communities of practice, and RDA outputs and recommendations; as well as domain-specific CODATA Working Groups, CODATA task groups, the WorldFAIR domain-specific case studies; Global Open Science Cloud case studies; and GO FAIR domain-specific networks.

Geographical approaches mostly consist of initiatives funded by a nation or region. Within national approaches, we found RDA national nodes; CODATA National Committees; WorldFAIR case studies; and Research Software Engineers national / multinational associations. Within regional approaches, we found RDA regions and other various regional initiatives.

The WP3 Landscape analysis service is building a knowledge base of selected resources to guide the Working Groups and integrate with other RDA TIGER services. The database creation process involves defining its purpose, identifying key data sources, and prioritising data ingestion processes to make community-endorsed initiatives easily discoverable and reusable. D3.1 set out the early vision for this work, and the design of a conceptual data model to describe and contextualise the landscape effectively.

Deliverable 3.1 was the first step towards building the landscape service, presenting the problem statement, the overall scope of the landscape analysis database, a plan for technical implementation, and a prioritised list of data sources to be included in the database. The document also presented the key next steps in the development, with the aim of creating a common community resource for RDA TIGER service provision. The service provision to the RDA TIGER supported groups was recognised as the next major test case for this service, improving the overall concept and testing its feasibility in real life situations.

3. Contribution of the RDA Maintenance Platform (RDA-MP) and Annotation tool to landscaping efforts

The RDA-MP aims to make it simpler and more useful to look for, link, access, and re-use RDA-affiliated entities, outputs, and supplementary resources, as well as relevant RDA-external resources from the wider research data landscape such as standards, publications, initiatives, and vocabularies. As a secondary objective, it aims to make it simpler, and more effective to classify, curate, publish, and preserve such outputs and resources - and the links between them. The RDA-MP contains a graph database of outputs, individuals, and other resources from the RDA and associated organisations, making it simple to link them to each other. Such resources can also be linked and classified in relation to RDA-external resources such as international standards, vocabularies, and publications, thus facilitating landscaping efforts. The database and associated infrastructure is designed to be flexible and allow for continuous community curation, and can also be adapted for use by particular groups (e.g. WGs) that wish to carry out their own landscape analyses.

The Annotation Tool is a browser plugin that allows the user to annotate and tag web resources using RDA vocabularies, making them available to the community through the RDA-MP. In addition, WP4 is also developing policies and procedures (e.g. curation procedures and vocabulary development); standards and benchmarks (e.g. annotation standards and metadata standards); and guidance and support solutions (e.g. annotation best practices and landscape analysis support).⁴

In this way, the outputs and services developed in WP4 contribute to landscaping efforts by providing tools that make it simpler for users to search, classify and share resources that are relevant to the topic at hand, as well as providing landscaping-related guidance and best practices. In particular, the Annotation Tool was developed to assist in landscaping analyses in RDA TIGER by making it easier to mobilise and reuse web-resources referred to in landscaping efforts. Materials added through the Annotation Tool are directly imported into the Graph Database through a Deposit Pipeline. These materials can then be browsed, along with the full knowledge base, using the RDA-MP web interface demo⁵. This makes it easy to browse, search, and filter resources by particular topics, individuals, and RDA vocabularies (see figure 1 below for an example).

Since D3.1 was published in June 2023, the services developed in WP4 have progressed significantly. Notably, the Graph Database has been significantly expanded, new versions of the Annotation Tool have been released, and the web interface demo was released. WP4 has developed new guidance materials such as the Annotation Tool Guidelines⁶, provided

⁴ For more information about the Maintenance Platform and other Output Services developed in WP4, see: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12568753>

⁵ <https://rda.dansdemo.nl/>

⁶

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/19Ret9G-h40-3Muz8HCzq4h08pHUzsCRMIMBnBVUMWV0/edit#heading=h.wcgh6zgsf3dp>

instruction to RDA TIGER members on how to use the above tools⁷, introduced the tools to TIGER-supported Working Groups, and demonstrated them at events such as the 21st RDA Plenary in Salzburg (October 2023).

Going forward, significant developments are planned to take place in time for the P23 RDA Plenary in November 2024, including further development of the Annotation Tool, Graph Database, and web interface, as well as preparations for a public launch of WP4 services to be discussed during the event.

Figure 1: Examples of Landscape Analysis Annotations in the RDA Catalogue - in this case, 'Infrastructures' of interest to Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER⁸.

The landscape analysis and output support services, including the RDA-MP and Annotation Tool, have been launched as demonstrator versions for RDA TIGER partners and select WGs. Once these services enter into production use, in most cases it makes sense to introduce them to a wider range of TIGER-supported WGs. A WG that would like to add their document library to the common RDA-MP database can be expected to have areas of landscape study where they could benefit from targeted support by the WP3 team. Similarly,

⁷

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1MEhxSUttOmw68IPTpwwsXKqYY_p1Gv-RP-kkIUnFLkl/edit#heading=h.28kh44kw8iix

⁸

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1MEhxSUttOmw68IPTpwwsXKqYY_p1Gv-RP-kkIUnFLkl/edit#heading=h.28kh44kw8iix, p.16

the landscape service will encourage WGs to be supported to make the results of the landscape study public, including through inclusion in the RDA-MP.

The initial mapping of the joint ‘user journey’ and the process the WG facilitators would use to introduce both of the services to the supported WGs was done in early July 2024. The model will be tested once the Maintenance Platform will be deemed ready for integration with the RDA website. From the sustainability point of view, both of the services (landscape and output service) will benefit from shortened lead time (in-kind service that can be provided as an add-on to already-supported WGs) and shorter time to completion (weeks or a few months instead of 12 to 18 months). Thus, these services can be optimised even in the last months of the project. Also, possible fee-carrying services based on them will require smaller financial commitments from the user communities compared to the facilitation service.

4. Developments in the OS landscape since D3.1 (June 2023)

Here we set out an updated overview of the main developments in the Open Science landscape since the publication of RDA TIGER D3.1⁹ in June 2023. This overview includes an update on the various categories of Open Science activity previously addressed in D3.1, as already listed here in section 2 above.

One element in the landscape described here is the current crop of RDA Working Groups (which is of course a category of particular importance to the RDA TIGER project). We hope that setting the WGs here alongside recent key developments in the OS landscape allows the reader to better understand the context in which these new WGs are operating, and the contemporaneous developments to which they should respond.

For consistency, we use the same overarching categories as set out in D3.1:

- first, **domain-agnostic** initiatives and activities; then
- **domain-specific** activities and initiatives, and finally
- **geographical** (regional and national) approaches.

Please refer to D3.1 for the full descriptions of each category including a summary of activity within each category up to June 2023: *to avoid duplication, such material will not be reproduced again within the current report*. Our emphasis in the current document is upon new developments in the last 15 months. For our complete view of the OS landscape from the start of the RDA TIGER project until the present moment of writing, D3.1 and the current report should be read together.

4.1 Developments in domain-agnostic initiatives

In this section we provide a summary of key domain-agnostic initiatives since the publication of RDA TIGER D3.1¹⁰.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

4.1.1. New domain-agnostic RDA Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER

RDA WGs are one element of the overall Open Science landscape, but clearly an element of high importance to the work of RDA TIGER. Those WGs that have been accepted for in-kind support (i.e., Facilitation, Communications, Landscape and Engagement and/or Output Services)¹¹, by RDA TIGER since June 2023, and therefore constitute relevant new developments within the landscape, include the following groups listed here.

4.1.1.1. Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG

The WG was one of the six pilot demonstrator WGs for the RDA TIGER project and has been receiving support from June 2023; its Case Statement was endorsed in July 2024. The WG Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data is a continuation of a previous RDA Interest Group, Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems' Data IG. The Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG is to produce recommendations for data and metadata coming from sUAS and autonomous platforms to support interoperability and reuse of these data in research data infrastructures. The WG will collect use cases of data collection and processing by uncrewed and autonomous platforms from different disciplines and document best practices. The co-chairs of the WG are based in Australasia (Australia), Africa (Botswana), and Europe (UK). At the time of writing, the WG is continuing its outreach activities, benefiting from a Landscape Awareness report compiled by the RDA TIGER Landscape and Engagement service. Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/small-uncrewed-aircraft-and-autonomous-platforms-data-working-group/>

4.1.1.2. Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)

The WG was one of the six pilot demonstrator WGs for the RDA TIGER project and has been receiving support from June 2023; its Case Statement was endorsed by RDA Council in September 2024. The community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG) will address a need in the community of data repositories and associated services worldwide: namely, how to extend the umbrella of trust, as exemplified by formal certification authorities such as ISO and CoreTrustSeal, to a wider range of service providers on which many repositories are dependent. The co-chairs of this WG are based in Australasia (New Zealand), Europe (Netherlands, Germany and the UK), and North America (USA). The WG is in its start-up phase and is looking to extend the geographical diversity of its membership at present. Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers/>

¹¹ See Table 1 and Table 2 for info on WG dates, etc. in RDA TIGER D5.2:
<https://zenodo.org/records/12599362>

4.1.1.3. RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption Working Group

This WG has been active since July 2023. The group aims to clarify the complementary relationship between the TRUST principles, certification processes, and metrics of other principle frameworks (FAIR, CARE, Data Repository Attributes). The group develops use cases that map the relationship between TRUST and other frameworks and a global survey of repositories around adoption of TRUST. There are two co-chairs from North America and one from Europe, working on use cases and a survey targeting a global audience. TIGER completed a landscape report to identify targets for the survey and other outreach in Central and South America and in Africa. The co-chairs and WG members' own networks extensively cover parts of the world to help foster global outreach. Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-trust-principles-outreach-and-adoption-working-group/>

4.1.1.4. EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG

The WG was endorsed by RDA Council in September 2022; RDA TIGER support was initiated in October 2023. The EOSC-Future & RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation Working Group (AIDV-WG) will address ethical, legal, and social challenges of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Data Visitation (DV) affecting of state-of-the art data technology impacting scientific exchange in the context of data sharing and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The WG is currently in its final stages, with four (of a planned five) outputs in the RDA Community Review stage. The WG has benefitted from extensive international collaboration between WG co-chairs and output authors based in Asia, Europe, Africa, North and South America. The co-chairs specifically are based in Türkiye, Belgium, Canada, USA, and Brazil. Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/>

4.1.1.5. RDA FAIR Mappings WG

Community Review ended on 29 August 2024. The group expects endorsement in late October 2024. RDA TIGER support began in January 2024. The FAIR Mappings WG aims at working with the various communities and the RDA WGs that have generated mappings to converge toward common guidelines to make different types of mappings FAIR, and a common machine-readable/actionable set of representations of the mappings beyond the capabilities of the current existing specifications. There are currently two co-chairs from Europe, so they need to recruit at least one non-European co-chair before endorsement. Internationalisation will also be necessary when collecting use cases of mappings and crosswalks. A challenge will be to identify communities working on mappings/crosswalks globally. The facilitator has completed some landscape work to identify potential stakeholders beyond Europe, with limited success. Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/>

4.1.1.6. Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG

At the time of writing, this WG has recently been approved for TIGER support in September 2024. It is currently working on its Case Statement which will be submitted for Community Review in October/November 2024. This WG will continue the work started in the (first)

[RDA Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group](#). This new WG will build on the results of the previous WG, proposing a collaboration with other RDA Groups (in particular the Global Open Research Commons WG) to develop its harmonised map of the Digital Research Tools Landscape. In particular, it will look to increase awareness of tool categories that research infrastructures should consider providing to their researchers, and give examples of these tools. The WG currently has three confirmed co-chairs (two in the UK and one in Saudi Arabia), and awaits confirmation of a fourth based in the USA.

4.1.1.7. RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations (DSTS) WG

The RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations Working Group was approved for RDA TIGER support in September 2023 and soon after endorsed by RDA Council in October 2023. The WG arose out of a widespread set of activities and interests in RDA and CODATA that have developed through close interaction with leading international, regional, and national organisations playing prominent roles in crisis preparedness and response, and rebuilding architecture, crisis governance, and the management of crisis situations. The WG's co-chairs are based in Australia (two), Türkiye (two), Belgium, and the UK. Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-codata-data-systems-tools-and-services-crisis-situations-wg/>

4.1.2. New domain-agnostic RDA Working Groups *not* supported by RDA TIGER

Since the publication of D3.1, there has been one approved new domain-agnostic RDA Working Group that, at the time of writing, is not receiving support from RDA TIGER. This is the Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive or Confidential Data: FAIRness for Controlled Data and Processes WG¹².

4.1.3. Domain-agnostic RDA Interest Groups

RDA Interest Groups continue to be more abundant in number than RDA Working Groups. This is partly due to the lack of requirement for Interest Groups to finish after completion of a specific term (in contrast, RDA Working Groups must complete substantive activity within approximately 18 months). This also means there is a lower rate of turnover compared to Working Groups. D3.1 found that 42 of 65 current Interest Groups are domain-agnostic. Based on the information available from the RDA website¹³, there are currently 61 active Interest Groups (not including those listed online but not yet endorsed), 48 of which can be understood as domain-agnostic. This maintains a similar proportion to the situation in June 2023.

We continue to consider the RDA Interest Groups as a category of activity that is worth monitoring, in particular because new Working Groups often arise from issues identified or

¹²

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/trusted-research-environments-for-sensitive-or-confidential-data-fairness-for-controlled-data-and-processes-wg/>

¹³ https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group

as continuation of activities that begin in Interest Groups. For example, the RDA TIGER-supported Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data Working Group developed from the Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems' Data IG¹⁴, and the RDA TIGER-supported RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG emerged from the RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG¹⁵.

4.1.4. RDA outputs and recommendations (domain-agnostic)

The presentation of RDA Outputs and Recommendations has changed somewhat online since June 2023. There are now clear definitions offered online of an RDA Recommendation and an Output, and how these differ¹⁶. At the time of writing, 121 RDA outputs and recommendations are available online¹⁷. Of these, the highest-priority category is that of Working Group Recommendations which have been officially reviewed and endorsed. These constitute the most important or 'flagship' results of RDA activity¹⁸. This category includes 34 Recommendations at the time of writing¹⁹. Of this group, 28 Recommendations appear to be domain-agnostic. A further five Recommendations are listed as currently undergoing community review or Council review, four of which appear to be domain-agnostic. These observations confirm the trend that domain-agnostic work around tools, infrastructure and approaches to FAIR data constitute the majority of these high-level outputs from RDA activity.

4.1.5. RDA Pathways

The most recent overview available online of RDA Pathways dates from July 2023²⁰, prepared for Plenary 21. The pathways can be used to search for groups directly on the RDA website²¹.

A group can belong to more than one pathway and a group should choose the relevant pathways as part of the setup process. There are ten Pathways presented, as follows:

- I. 'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Principles'
- II. 'FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation & Deployment'
- III. 'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Institutional'
- IV. 'Data Infrastructures & Environments - Regional and Disciplinary'

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/small-unmanned-aircraft-systems-data-ig/group-messages/>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-certification-digital-repositories-ig/>

¹⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/what-are-recommendations-and-outputs/>

¹⁷

https://www.rd-alliance.org/outputs/?keyword=&output-status%5B%5D=in-community-review&output-status%5B%5D=in-council-review-open&start_date=&end_date=&sort-by=date-desc

¹⁸ "RDA Recommendations are produced by RDA WGs. They are the official, endorsed results of the RDA and considered our 'flagship' Outputs."

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/what-are-recommendations-and-outputs/>

¹⁹

https://www.rd-alliance.org/outputs/?keyword=&output-type%5B%5D=working-group-recommendation&output-status%5B%5D=endorsed&start_date=&end_date=&sort-by=date-desc

²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-pathways/>

²¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/>

- V. 'Data Infrastructures & Environments - International'
- VI. 'Training, Stewardship & Data Management Planning'
- VII. 'Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation'
- VIII. 'Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward'
- IX. 'Discipline Focused Data Issues'
- X. 'Research Software'

This list represents one less Pathway than the prior version of the list, but the themes of infrastructure, and of sets of principles, continue to be strong. Clearly most of the pathways are domain-agnostic; indeed the Pathways list here has been designed to gather all the domain-specific issues in one dedicated Pathway, 'Discipline Focused Data Issues'. The RDA Landscape Analysis Service will continue to track the pathways from each plenary as a means of understanding the plenary-based conceptualisation of key issues in the RDA ecosystem.

4.1.6. EOSC activities including EOSC-funded projects, EOSC SRIA and EOSC Task Forces

4.1.6.1. INFRAEOSC Work Programme

As noted in D3.1, a cohort of EOSC-funded projects had recently started under the Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC 2022 programme, 'Enabling an operational, open and FAIR EOSC ecosystem (INFRAEOSC)', with a mission to align and work towards a common EOSC vision via the topics of ESFRI, Open Science, Oceans, Neuroscience, and Science Instrumentation; some are domain-agnostic while others tackle FAIR implementation in a specific discipline.

Since then, the high tempo of activity has continued. The INFRAEOSC 2023 call for proposals for funding, focused on the topics of The European Open Science Cloud, Community-based Software, and Tracking Knowledge Production, resulted in seven new projects signing a grant agreement, with a start date of early 2024 and a heavier emphasis across the cohort on domain-agnostic problems. The Research Infrastructures Work Programme opened for proposals in December 2023, with the topics of FAIR and open data sharing, EOSC Partnership, and Innovative and customizable services for EOSC Exchange. At the time of writing, the successful projects from this round are confirming their grant agreement and so have not yet been publicly announced. June 2024 saw the launch of the call for proposals for HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-02-01, focused on a single topic, 'Future Engagement Model for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation', and so we continue to see specialisation of focus on the priorities of operationalising the EOSC Federation as a functional human and technical infrastructure. RDA TIGER will continue to track the funded projects and thematic topics of the INFRAEOSC work programme²² as well as the activities of European e-infrastructures that continue to interoperate closely with the

22

https://rea.ec.europa.eu/funding-and-grants/horizon-europe-research-infrastructures/enabling-operational-open-and-fair-eosc-ecosystem-infraeosc_en

EOSC (for example GEANT²³, OpenAIRE²⁴, EGI²⁵); ESFRI Research Infrastructures²⁶, and the fourteen emerging European data spaces²⁷.

4.1.6.2. EOSC SRIA

The EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)²⁸, described as v1.1 in D3.1, was comprised of the following twelve action areas, identified as areas of activity needed to implement EOSC:

- I. Persistent Identifiers
- II. Metadata and Ontologies
- III. FAIR Metrics and Certification
- IV. Authentication and authorisation infrastructure - AAI
- V. User Environments
- VI. EOSC Interoperability Framework
- VII. Resource Provider Environments
- VIII. Rules of Participation
- IX. Landscape monitoring
- X. Skills and training
- XI. Rewards and recognition
- XII. Widening to public and private sectors and going global.²⁹

Since then a new version of the SRIA, version 1.2³⁰, was published in December 2023. It is not intended to be a full update of the EOSC SRIA, and was published primarily in order to include the new Multi Annual Roadmap (MAR)³¹. However a limited reorganisation of the list of action areas has taken place - we now see the first seven areas of activity from the 2022 list grouped together as "Implementation Challenges", and the following five activity areas ("Rules of participation" through to "Widening to public and private sectors and going global") grouped together as "Boundary Conditions", supplemented by two further activity areas, "Funding models" and "Communication". This again suggests a shift from domain-specific investigation and an increasing focus upon pragmatic operationalisation of the EOSC. SRIA 2.0 is expected to be published in the first quarter of 2025³².

This overview of activity areas continues to provide useful categories which can be incorporated into the knowledge base of the Landscape Analysis Service.

²³ <https://geant.org>

²⁴ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

²⁵ <https://www.egi.eu/>

²⁶

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/esfri_en

²⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

²⁸ <https://eosc.eu/sria-mar>

²⁹ <https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/SRIA%201.1%20final.pdf>

³⁰ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf

³¹ https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/20231114_SRIA_1.2_final2.pdf, p. 2.

³² <https://eosc.eu/sria-2-0-community-consultation/>

4.1.6.3. EOSC Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups

D3.1 tracked thirteen task forces under four domain-agnostic headings: Metadata; Research Careers; Technical Challenges; and Sustaining EOSC. This cohort of task forces has now completed its term:

“Following the completion of the two-year mandate of the original EOSC-A Task Forces in December 2023, a comprehensive assessment was undertaken by the EOSC-A Board of Directors in interaction with the Task Forces. The Board not only determined the continuation, suspension, or reconfiguration of existing TFs, but also reached a consensus on the creation of new TFs. A call for Task Force members was open from 21 March to 21 April 2024, and attracted 206 applications from 22 countries. The new Task Forces kicked off their activities in June and July 2024.”³³

The number of task forces has been dramatically reduced following this review. The four new EOSC task forces are:

- EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force
- FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force
- Health Data Task Force
- EOSC-A Long-Term Data Retention Task Force

Task forces are expected to liaise with the INFRAEOSC projects as above, and also with the six current EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups as follows:

OA Expert Group 1: Persistent Identifiers

OA Expert Group 2: Metadata, Ontologies and Interoperability

OA Expert Group 3: FAIR Assessment and Alignment

OA Expert Group 4: User and Resource Environments

OA Expert Group 5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling

OA Expert Group 6: Open Scholarly Communication

These six EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups are a ‘bottom-up’ initiative that emerged from the EOSC Winter Schools initiative, and informed by work by the EOSC Focus support project³⁴. Particularly as a reflection of the priorities of Open Science-sector priorities, these expert groups offer another track of domain-agnostic activity of which the Landscape service should be aware.

4.1.7. Domain-agnostic CODATA Task Groups

Domain-agnostic CODATA Task Groups have remained stable in number after a cohort of successful applications in October 2023. D3.1 reported four domain-agnostic task groups in the 2021-2023 cohort. This number of domain-agnostic task groups has been maintained, alongside the long-running Fundamental Physical Constants task group^{35,36}.

³³ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-task-forces>

³⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

³⁵ <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/fundamental-physical-constants/>

³⁶ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/>

- Advancing Data Science for Sustainability³⁷
- CODATA-WDS TG on Citizen-generated data for the SDGs³⁸
- Data Ethics Task Group (DETG)³⁹
- Digital Representation of Units of Measurement (DRUM)⁴⁰.

This set of task groups deals with a range of widely-applicable data science, fundamental science and ethical issues relating to data and Open Science. Accordingly, those who are interested in initiating an RDA WG in a related area should be aware of these existing Task Groups, their progress, personnel and outputs.

4.1.8. Domain-agnostic CODATA Working Groups

As noted in D3.1, CODATA Working Groups⁴¹ differ from task groups in that a working group is expected to complete its activity within a set period of not normally more than two years.

The following Working Group has been approved by the General Assembly in 2023: The role of integrity in data and AI science, ethics, and policy (Integrity-WG).

Several further Working Groups are active under and alongside the CODATA Making Data Work - WorldFAIR+ programme⁴² - in particular, the Research Data Management Terminology (RDMT) Working Group⁴³; the Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) Working Groups, discussed below; and the OneGeochemistry Working Group which was established as a result of the WorldFAIR project and will be included in domain-specific initiatives, below. Again, proposed RDA WGs on related areas of focus should be aware of the progress, personnel and outputs from these activities.

4.1.9. The Global Open Science Cloud initiative

The Global Open Science Cloud initiative is described in D3.1. The methodology includes domain-agnostic working groups and domain-specific case studies. Four initial WG topics were undertaken in the first two year period: Strategy, governance and sustainability; Policy and legal; Technical infrastructure; and Data interoperability. The WGs completed in December 2023, having reported at a GOSC All Hands Meeting and IDW sessions in October 2023. The work of the Policy WG is being continued by the CODATA International Data Policy Committee⁴⁴, while that of the Interoperability WG is being continued through the

³⁷ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/advancing-data-science-for-sustainability/>

³⁸ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/citizen-science-for-the-sustainable-development-goals/>

³⁹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/data-ethics/>

⁴⁰ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/drum/>

⁴¹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/working-groups/>

⁴² <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work-worldfair/>

⁴³ <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/rdm-terminology-wg/> - this WG differs from others in that it is revived for a review of the RDMT every two years after a fresh open call for members.

⁴⁴ <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-policy/international-data-policy-committee/>

work on the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)⁴⁵. Meanwhile, the GOSC IPO⁴⁶ continues to explore opportunities and technical alignment. New emphasis is being placed on capacity building. Training activities were delivered in Kenya during February 2024, associated with the VizAfrica conference⁴⁷ hosted by JKUAT, the Kenyan National CODATA Committee⁴⁸ and the Training and Capacity Building Node of the African Open Science Platform⁴⁹. Training activities are planned for Mongolia in November 2024. The regular CNIC-CODATA Training Workshop⁵⁰ will also take place in November 2024. (Domain-specific GOSC case studies are discussed in section 4.2.10. below.)

In sum, the GOSC initiative successfully completed its first phase and contributed to important work related to WorldFAIR⁵¹. Funding proposals have been made to reinforce the coordinating mechanism and for technical alignment and capacity building work. Pending the outcome of these proposals, the work and the collaborations created in GOSC are being continued through other CODATA activities and through the work of the GOSC IPO.

4.1.10. The WorldFAIR project and its cross-domain activities

D3.1 set out the cross-domain concerns of the WorldFAIR project^{52,53} and its approach to understanding how different disciplines can align on data challenges such as FAIR data, data management and stewardship, and the co-design of interoperability workflows. The project completed in May 2024 and work continues on one of the key outputs, the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)⁵⁴. The CDIF is continuing to be developed by a working group drawing expertise, via an open call to the global Open Science community, from a wide range of organisations and data-related professions. WorldFAIR outputs, particularly the CDIF, are highly relevant to the work of existing or new RDA working groups concerned with the interoperability of research data - particularly technical interoperability.

4.1.11. The FAIR-IMPACT project and its cross-domain activities

The FAIR-IMPACT project (June 2022 - May 2025) builds on the practices, policies, tools and technical specifications arising from FAIRsFAIR, other H2020 projects and initiatives, and from the FAIR and other relevant Working Groups of the former EOSC Executive Board, to support the implementation of FAIR-enabling practices, tools and services across scientific communities at European, national and institutional levels. FAIR-IMPACT identifies practices, policies, tools and technical specifications to guide researchers, repository managers, research performing organisations, policy makers and citizen scientists towards a

⁴⁵ <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work-worldfair/cdif/>

⁴⁶ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/global-open-science-cloud/gosc-ipo/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.aicad.or.ke/vizafrika/>

⁴⁸ <https://codata.org/kenya/>

⁴⁹ <https://aosp.org.za/>

⁵⁰ <http://intertraining2024.codata.cn/>

⁵¹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work-worldfair/worldfair/>

⁵² <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work-worldfair/worldfair/>,

⁵³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/>

⁵⁴ <https://worldfair-project.eu/cross-domain-interoperability-framework/>,
<https://zenodo.org/records/11236871>

FAIR data management cycle⁵⁵. Domain-agnostic themes tackled by FAIR-IMPACT are persistent identifiers (PIDs), metadata, ontologies, metrics, certification and interoperability, and RDA working groups should be prepared to interoperate with FAIR-IMPACT outputs. The project's domain-specific activities are included in section 4.2., and national approaches in section 4.3.

4.1.12. The Global Open Research Commons typology of elements

D3.1 describes the GORC activity⁵⁶ and particularly its typology of elements - essential concepts describing a set of attributes that are part of commons development, defined in order to identify a set of core functions and activities that the GORC will focus upon, divided into digital and social/human elements. This typology has been added to the RDA-MP (see section 3) and provides a set of criteria against which the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service can regularly check for activities created under these categories.

4.1.13. The Research Software Alliance (ReSA) task forces

ReSA Task Forces described in D3.1 are as follows:

- Code Availability;
- Database of Research Software Funding Opportunities;
- Research Institution Policies to Support Research Software.

Since June 2023, three new task forces⁵⁷ have been launched:

- Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS)⁵⁸: this is a joint RDA and ReSA TF, which was officially endorsed in November 2023, and which is supported by RDA-TIGER. The working group aims to promote the implementation of research software policies at the research institution level;
- Research Software Authorship and Contribution TF⁵⁹: this aims to define criteria for software authorship and describe contribution types/roles in research software; and most recently;
- The Actionable Guidelines for Making Research Software FAIR TF⁶⁰ which aims to develop actionable guidelines for making research software FAIR aimed at researchers. At the time of writing, this TF was in the process of finding co-chairs.

⁵⁵ <https://www.fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-expanding-fair-solutions-across-eosc>

⁵⁶ WG: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/activity/> and IG: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/activity/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/>

⁵⁸

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/rda-resa-policies-in-research-organisations-for-research-software-pro4rs/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.researchsoft.org/tf-authorship-contribution/>

⁶⁰ Current proposal draft

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/15srfB15eq9I5jKTSTMF_MIFZfGwX8qx8

4.1.14. Various relevant domain-agnostic advisory organisations

D3.1 recommended that consideration should be given to organisations that generate policy, position statements and recommendations applicable to multiple domains in the research data space, and whose work is likely to be relevant to those considering the establishment of a new RDA WG. Examples provided include bodies such as Knowledge Exchange, Science Europe, the Digital Curation Centre, the Digital Preservation Coalition and GO FAIR. RDA TIGER continues to monitor the outputs of these organisations where these are relevant to Open Science and research data.

4.2. Developments in domain-specific initiatives

In this section we provide an overview of the main developments in key *domain-specific* initiatives in the Open Science landscape since the publication of RDA TIGER D3.1 in June 2023. Again, please refer to D3.1 for the full descriptions of each category including a summary of activity within each category up to June 2023: to avoid duplication, such material will *not* be reproduced again here within the current report.

4.2.1. New domain-specific RDA Working Groups

RDA WGs that have been accepted for support by RDA TIGER since June 2023, and thus constitute notable new developments for our project's view of the landscape, are listed in this section.

4.2.1.1. FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG

The WG was one of the six pilot demonstrator WGs for the RDA TIGER project, and has been receiving support from June 2023; its Case Statement was endorsed by RDA Council in June 2024. The FAIRification of Genomic Annotations Working Group (FGA-WG) focuses on the challenges of harmonising metadata and software solutions to improve the discovery and reuse of publicly available 'genomic annotation' data. Genomic annotations, sometimes referred to as 'genomic tracks', refer to data files that annotate reference sequence positions and can be visualised in genome browsers or analysed often non-visually using computational tools that span the domains of life science (e.g., statistical colocalization analyses). The FGA-WG aims to establish a minimal metadata schema based on the harmonisation of existing schemas and recommendations, working to gradually improve this schema based on the interrogation of a set of use cases. The co-chairs of the WG are based in Europe (Norway and Italy) and North America (USA and Canada), with the WG membership largely drawing from these regions and also from Australia.

Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fairification-genomic-annotations-wg/>

4.2.1.2. Wind Energy Community Standards WG

RDA TIGER support was initiated in October 2022, with the WG endorsed by RDA Council in April 2024. The goal of the WG is to reduce data management overhead within and between organisations working with wind energy. This will be done by firstly creating a recommendation document, "Guidelines for improving FAIR data maturity in wind energy in practice". This will then be used to create a wind energy FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP),

which is a methodology developed within the GO FAIR initiative⁶¹. The FIP will give the scientific and research communities the opportunity to express their choices of standards, technologies, tools and procedures by which they fulfil the FAIR principles. The group is currently carrying out engagement activities in coordination with RDA TIGER Facilitation, Communications, and Landscape and Engagement services. This includes engagement with initiatives outside Europe and North America, and also with groups within RDA whose focus is on metadata schemas and development of FAIR practices and semantic artefacts. WG co-chairs represent Europe (Switzerland) and North America (USA), though additional co-chairs are actively being sought to broaden the WG's geographical diversity. Webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/wind-energy-community-standards-wg/>

4.2.1.3. RDA Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities WG

Community Review is complete and the WG was endorsed in September 2024 with the kick-off meeting of the group on 26 September 2024. Focus is on aligning approaches to vocabulary creation and extension and FAIRification of multilingual controlled vocabularies. The group is building on European level work (OPERAS, SSHOC, TRIPLE). There are two co-chairs from Europe and one from Australia. The challenge is to achieve greater geographic diversity in the WG membership (currently mostly Europe and Australia). Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/alignment-of-multilingual-vocabularies-in-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-wg/>

4.2.1.4. RDA Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG

This WG is working on revisions in response to community review at the time of writing. The aim is to create a Health Data Commons Global Open Research Commons (GORC) profile. To do this, the WG wants to bring together health data commons in all stages of development. The aims of the group are inherently global, with the intention to recruit use cases from across the globe. Co-chairs are from Europe (2), North America (1) and Asia (1). The challenge will be to recruit an equally global membership and use cases of health data commons to achieve the aims of the group. Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/health-data-commons-gorc-profile-wg/>

4.2.1.5. Ethics in Agricultural (AG) Data WG

This Working Group was endorsed by RDA Council in late July 2024, with RDA TIGER support beginning in September 2024. The WG will address the ethical issues related to the treatment of agricultural data, focusing especially on the challenges and risks for the most marginalised actors in the data value chains: smallholder farmers and indigenous people. These groups are expected or asked to contribute data and be transparent, but have no voice in how data are used and are often not the beneficiaries of the data revolution and digital transformation in general to which they contribute. The co-chairs of the WG are based in Europe (Italy) and North America (USA). Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/ethics-in-agricultural-ag-data-wg/>

⁶¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>

4.2.1.6. Computational Modelling of Health Data WG

RDA TIGER support for this WG began in September 2024. At this stage, the WG has yet to produce its Case Statement, and will use support provided by RDA TIGER to guide it through the Case Statement development process as well as for the recruitment of new WG co-chairs and members. This WG will develop a curated community resource of data features, synthetic and simulated health datasets for research, open-source software, protocols and workflows, to make computational modelling of health data a more accessible and findable resource. The WG will aim to bring together various experts from the area of medical research, computer science, consumer participation and ethics to form a global multidisciplinary Working Group collaborating on improving the creation and use of computational health data models. The sole confirmed co-chair of the WG at the time of writing is based in Australia. The webpage for this group is not yet available.

4.2.1.7. Building Immune Digital Twins WG

This Working Group was approved for TIGER support in October 2023, receiving endorsement from RDA Council in August 2024. The WG Building Immune Digital Twins aims to foster a network of collaborators and experts in all relevant research areas to do with immune digital twins, including immunologists, clinicians, mathematical modellers, and software engineers. The ultimate goal of the WG is to help create a long-term interdisciplinary immune digital twin community willing to take on the challenges of this new field of research. Its planned deliverables are: i) Literature repository; ii) Model repository and model metadata catalogue; iii) Building IDT best practices recommendation document. The co-chairs of the WG are based in Europe (Germany, France, Belgium), North America (three in USA), and Asia (India, Japan). Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/building-immune-digital-twins-wg/>

4.2.1.8. Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG

This Working Group was one of the first two Groups who successfully applied for RDA TIGER support via the Open Call procedure. The WG's RDA TIGER support began in June 2023, with the WG officially endorsed by RDA Council in March 2024. The WG brings together experts in materials science and related domains such as chemistry and nanomaterials, to focus on increasing uptake of the FAIR Principles in materials research (in particular in connection with Interoperability and Reusability), supported by improved resources, in particular widely-agreed and FAIR terminologies, metadata and ontologies. The objectives of the WG include collecting and reviewing existing vocabularies, terminologies, schemas etc. for the material sciences and cognate domains such as chemistry, and proposing and verifying best practices for materials science practitioners to achieve FAIR data based on terminologies, schema, ontologies, etc. The co-chairs of the WG are based in Asia (South Korea, Japan), Europe (two in the UK) and North America (two in USA). Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/harmonised-terminologies-and-schemas-fair-data-materials-science-and-related-domains-wg/group-messages/>

4.2.1.9. Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG

This Working Group was endorsed by RDA Council in June 2024; it successfully applied for RDA TIGER support, which started in the same month. The WG focuses on multi-omics data integration across multiple Omics data types (e.g., genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, phenomics, etc.), leveraging a wide range of high-throughput technologies as a holistic approach to quantification and characterisation of large complex pools of biological molecules. The WG aims to address challenges in this area by creating a matrix of identified reporting guidelines and standards essential for integration of multiple Omics metadata elements across the different domain technologies. The WG's co-chairs are based in Europe (Belgium) and North America (two in USA). Webpage:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/multi-omics-metadata-standards-integration-momsi-wg>

4.2.2. New domain-specific RDA Working Groups *not* supported by RDA TIGER

Since the publication of D3.1, there have been two new domain-agnostic RDA Working Groups that, at the time of writing, are not receiving support from RDA TIGER. These are:

- Optical Radiation Exposure and Visual Experience Data WG⁶²;
- Coordinating Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes WG⁶³.

4.2.3. New domain-specific RDA Interest Groups

As discussed in section 4.1.3., above, 13 of 61 currently-active Interest Groups (not including those listed online but not yet endorsed) can be considered domain-specific, which represents a slight decrease in the proportion of all current interest groups from D3.1. These groups are mostly focused on the natural sciences domains, including biodiversity; chemistry; earth, space and environmental data; geospatial data: water data; life sciences: materials data: photon and neutron science; salmon tracking; and health. The remaining three groups partly or wholly pertain to the human sciences: health data (a cross-domain research area including natural science and social science); linguistics; and psychology.

4.2.4. New domain-specific RDA communities of practice

In June 2023 there was one publicly listed RDA community of practice. Another nascent community of practice is now listed online, but does not yet appear to be operational: “The Improving Earth and Environmental Sciences Data evolves from the RDA/ESIP Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Interest Group. We are currently developing our “agreement” statement. The chairs have not been decided yet.”⁶⁴ RDA TIGER will continue to monitor developments within RDA Communities of Practice.

⁶² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/optical-radiation-exposure-and-visual-experience-data-wg/>

⁶³

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/coordinating-earth-space-and-environmental-science-data-preservation-and-scholarly-publication-processes-wg/>

⁶⁴ https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=community-of-practice

4.2.5. New RDA outputs and recommendations

As discussed above in section 4.1.4., the majority (28 of 34) of endorsed RDA recommendations and supporting outputs are domain-agnostic. The remaining six domain-specific outputs address the domains of health science, agriculture and nutrition (including wheat data), COVID-19, and linguistics.

RDA's work in EOSC Future promised the release of domain-specific information sheets. These sheets were published in September 2023 and are available for the following fields: Biodiversity; Chemistry; Climate Change in the Arctic; Cultural Heritage; Earth Space and Environmental Sciences; Linguistics; Materials Sciences and Engineering; and Social Sciences⁶⁵.

4.2.6. New domain-specific CODATA Working Groups

The Onegeochemistry Working Group⁶⁶ emerged in 2023 from the Geochemistry case study of the WorldFAIR project. The OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group's mission is to advance geoscientific knowledge and discoveries by building and maintaining consensus-driven standards that make geochemistry research data globally findable and accessible, and truly interoperable and reusable to both humans and machines. The WG is currently approved to run until October 2025, when it may be re-approved for continuation.

4.2.7. New domain-specific CODATA Task Groups

In addition to the domain-agnostic task groups described above in section 4.1.7, the following domain-specific TGs⁶⁷ were approved or renewed at the CODATA General Assembly held in October 2023:

- Data driven social change towards society promoting cognitively healthy ageing⁶⁸
- Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations Task Group (DSTS_CS-TG)⁶⁹
- FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research (FAIR-DRR)⁷⁰
- Geographical Indications Environment and Sustainability (GIES)⁷¹.

In addition to the Task Groups listed above, the Fundamental Physical Constants Task Group has been recognised as a standing initiative of CODATA since 2016⁷².

⁶⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10026059>; also linked from

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-disciplines/>

⁶⁶ <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/worldfair/onegeochemistry-wg/>

⁶⁷ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/>

⁶⁸

<https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/data-driven-social-change-towards-society-promoting-cognitively-healthy-aging/>

⁶⁹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/data-systems-tools-and-services-for-crisis-situations/>

⁷⁰ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/fair-data-for-disaster-risk-research/>

⁷¹ <https://codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/geographical-indications-environment-and-sustainability/>

⁷² <https://codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/fundamental-physical-constants/>

4.2.8. The WorldFAIR Project case studies

Eleven case studies addressing specific research domains or cross-domain research areas were completed by the WorldFAIR project between June 2022 and May 2024⁷³. These address the following domains or cross-domain research areas: chemistry; materials science, specifically nanomaterials; geochemistry; social studies; population health; urban health; biodiversity; agricultural biodiversity; ocean science; disaster risk reduction; and cultural heritage. Whilst exact methods vary, each case study provides detailed insight from domain researchers - via openly published reports⁷⁴ and FAIR Implementation Profiles⁷⁵ - into current considerations of the state of FAIR data and the challenges for technical interoperability across each research area and between domains. Existing and proposed RDA working groups in these domains, or cross-domain research areas, should familiarise themselves with these outputs.

4.2.9. The FAIR-IMPACT project use cases

The FAIR-IMPACT project is described in section 4.1.11., above. The project includes support for use cases in four important domain areas:

- agri-food;
- life science;
- social sciences and humanities;
- photon and neutron sciences.

RDA working groups in these areas should consult the FAIR-IMPACT directory⁷⁶ where results can be filtered by domain, and familiarise themselves with relevant FAIR-IMPACT outputs.

4.2.10. Global Open Science Cloud domain-specific case studies

The GOSC domain-specific case studies were completed in December 2023, following reports at the GOSC All Hands Meeting and International Data Week sessions in October 2023. The biodiversity / camera trap data case study contributed to the work of WorldFAIR WP09, Biodiversity⁷⁷. The public health case study contributed to WorldFAIR WP07⁷⁸ and the activity is continuing through the new Wellcome-funded Data Science Without Borders project⁷⁹. The GOSC IPO, meanwhile, is continuing to support the work of the SDG-13 case study and exploring new funding opportunities.

⁷³ <https://worldfair-project.eu/case-studies/>

⁷⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁷⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project-fips/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

⁷⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases>

⁷⁷ <https://worldfair-project.eu/biodiversity/>

⁷⁸ <https://worldfair-project.eu/population-health/>

⁷⁹ <https://codata.org/launch-of-the-data-science-without-borders-project/>

4.3. Developments in regional and national approaches

As noted in D3.1, awareness of geographically-bound initiatives and organisations will help those who may wish to either set up an RDA Working Group with a geographical focus, or who simply wish to know of relevant people in various geographical areas with whom to collaborate. Geographically-bound initiatives may be domain-agnostic or domain-specific (and so may also be listed above) but their priority focus is to engage with a specific country or region. Interested readers should review section 3.4.2 of D3.1 for an initial overview of regionally-focused activities and initiatives, as that material will not be repeated here.

4.3.1. RDA National Nodes and Regions

No major developments since D3.1, when we found 27 ‘national nodes’ represented online; except the regions and national nodes are now combined into one list of ‘regional groups’⁸⁰. There are currently 30 groups listed in this category, with RDA Netherlands launching in June 2024.

4.3.2. EOSC FAIR Champions

Between January and March 2023, the FAIR-IMPACT project held an open call to recruit ‘FAIR Champions’: experts actively engaged in analysing and shaping FAIR data policies and practices in their field. Via the FAIR Champion role, these individuals identify research data gaps and needs within their communities, create broader engagement with FAIR, and shape and disseminate the outcomes of the FAIR-IMPACT project⁸¹. The cohort of 13 includes one person each to represent Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Romania, Spain, Switzerland, and the UK, and two representatives for Italy. There is a national dimension to this work: the EOSC FAIR Champions are involved in facilitating national roadshows in their country, and contribute to the development of FAIR implementation stories via the FAIR-IMPACT project⁸².

4.3.3. CODATA National Committees

The nature and number (nineteen) of CODATA National Committees⁸³ remains stable, with no major developments since D3.1.

4.3.4. WorldFAIR case studies

All WorldFAIR case studies - which concluded by May 2024 - now present their findings online⁸⁴, as noted in sections 4.1.10. and 4.2.8. above. These not only offer findings specific to domains and cross-domain research areas, but also offer opportunities for engagement with their respective national scientific communities.

⁸⁰ https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=regional-group

⁸¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/open-call-european-fair-champions>

⁸² <https://fair-impact.eu/eosc-fair-champions>

⁸³ <https://codata.org/membership/national-members/>

⁸⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/worldfair-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

4.3.5. Research Software Engineers national / multinational associations

D3.1 reported that National/Multinational (RSE) Associations represent the RSE communities from specific countries, including: Belgium, Germany, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand, United States and Denmark.

During the Research Software Engineering Conference (RSECon)⁸⁵, the RSE Worldwide session⁸⁶ provided an overview of all RSE and similar associations from around the globe. Most notable organisations growing in importance outside of Europe are RSSE Africa and RSE Asia Association. A recent ReSA blog post⁸⁷ provides a summary of this session.

4.3.6. Other regional initiatives and networks

The RDA TIGER team provided an overview in D3.1 of international activities bound by a regional or national focus. Recent updates to that list are added here.

4.3.6.1. Africa

- The Digital Hub for Open Research in East Africa is a new INASP project funded by the Templeton World Charity Foundation⁸⁸. This project aims to harness the transformative potential of Open Science in East Africa by empowering young researchers who address critical questions facing their nations and communities. The project team plans to do this by establishing a digital East African open research learning hub, with a focus on Kenya, Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda.
- Launched in February 2024, the The Data Science Without Borders (DSWB) project will operate for three years. This project is a collaborative initiative receiving technical oversight from the Africa Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Africa CDC). DSWB will be implemented in three African institutions, including the Armauer Hansen Research Institute (AHRI) in Ethiopia, Douala General Hospital (DGH) in Cameroon, and the Institute for Health Research—Epidemiological Surveillance and Training (IRESSEF) in Senegal, with leadership from the project lead, Dr. Agnes Kiragga from the African Population and Health Research Center, Kenya. In collaboration with key technical partners including the London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM), UK; the Committee on Data (CODATA), France; Makerere Artificial Intelligence Lab (Mak AI Lab), Uganda; and the Open Science Program Office (OSPO Now), UK; the project's primary goal is to co-design strategies that leverage advanced data science tools, including machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI), that will leverage locally generated data sets to address locally derived research questions that aim to improve African health outcomes⁸⁹.

⁸⁵ <https://rsecon24.society-rse.org/>

⁸⁶ <https://rsecon24.society-rse.org/programme/rse-worldwide/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.researchsoft.org/blog/2024-09-24/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.templetonworldcharity.org/projects-resources/project-database/33195>

⁸⁹

<https://aphrc.org/blogarticle/building-data-science-capacity-across-africa-the-data-science-without-borders-pathfinder-tour/>

- The South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR)⁹⁰ is a national centre with a focus on all official languages of South Africa, supporting research and development in the domains of language technologies and language-related studies in the humanities and social sciences.
- Africa Information Highway⁹¹ is a network of live open data platforms (ODPs) electronically linking all African countries and 16 regional organisations. The overall objective is to significantly increase public access to official and other statistics across Africa, while at the same time supporting African countries to improve data quality, management, and dissemination.
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)⁹² aims to provide a World-class infrastructure and services for the West and Central African Research and Education community for development.

4.3.6.2. Americas

- The RDA-US launched its Targeted International Working GRoups - US Program, (TIGRUS) in late 2023. The program, still in its pilot phase, has worked closely with RDA TIGER (in particular the RDA TIGER Facilitation Service) to develop its own support service⁹³. TIGRUS assists the RDA-US community in tackling data challenges specific to the United States and amplifying results that are achieved through RDA in collaboration efforts with the international RDA community. At present, it is supporting two RDA Working Groups in extending the impact of their outputs in the USA; these WGs are National PID Strategies WG⁹⁴ and the DMP Common Standards WG⁹⁵.
- The Digital Research Alliance of Canada is an EOSC observer organisation with its own system of working groups and staff as well as working groups that engage with RDA.

4.3.6.3. Australasia

- Australian Research Data Commons is a key infrastructure provider and advocacy organisation for research data in Australia, that is government-funded, works closely with research communities, develops thematic research commons, and facilitates skills development and training work.
- Australian Scalable Drone Cloud (ASDC)⁹⁶ is a scalable open-source platform for users of drone data. The platform's objective is to service all aspects of the Australian drone user community, including citizen scientists, NGOs, and government. The platform is being built with the goal of accelerating widespread adoption of FAIR Principles for drone-acquired data from the point of capture to publication⁹⁷.

⁹⁰ <https://sadilar.org/en/>

⁹¹ <https://www.afdb.org/en/knowledge/statistics/africa-information-highway-aih>

⁹² <https://wacren.net/en/>

⁹³ <https://rdaus.org/rda-us-launches-tigrus-facilitation-program/>

⁹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/>

⁹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg/>

⁹⁶ <https://asdc.io/>

⁹⁷ This description adapted from <https://asdc.io/about>.

4.3.6.4. Europe

- Various Competence Centres - national level community-based networks focusing knowledge, skills, facilitating training around RDS and data stewardship - are establishing an active profile in Europe, including:
 - Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Networks⁹⁸
 - Irish Data Stewardship Network Sonraí⁹⁹
 - The Dutch Data Steward Interest Group (DSIG)¹⁰⁰, which has been running since 2017, and has hosted domain-specific sessions under the Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDCCs) umbrella since May 2023¹⁰¹.
- NFDI¹⁰² is a national research infrastructure in Germany, with a coordinated network of thematic consortia. Base4NFDI¹⁰³ provides basic services across various consortia.
- The European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence (EVERSE)¹⁰⁴ is an EU-funded project which aims at building a European quality network for research software.

4.3.6.5. CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science

In August 2024, the ninth annual CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science and Advanced Data Science Workshop took place at the International Center for Theoretical Physics in Trieste, Italy¹⁰⁵. Whilst this long-running initiative is not focused on one geographic area, it prioritises early career researchers from developing economies, and provides high quality training in essential data science, research data management and data visualisation techniques and skills along with the opportunity for participants to foster professional relationships within and across national and regional groupings.

5. Discussion

In this section we reflect briefly on some visible trends with particular emphasis on recent developments in the Open Science landscape summarised above.

5.1. Value of engagement with RDA, particularly RDA TIGER activity

The overview in section 4 above sets out the valuable work currently underway across a range of current and recent initiatives and groups. Emerging and new RDA WGs clearly have the opportunity to draw upon and benefit from this rich landscape of activities.

⁹⁸ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network>

⁹⁹ <https://datastewards.ie/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/>

¹⁰¹ <https://tdcc.nl/dsig/history/>

¹⁰² <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

¹⁰³ <https://base4nfdi.de/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://everse.software/>

¹⁰⁵

<https://www.datascienceschools.org/9th-codata-rda-school-of-research-data-science-trieste-august-2024/>

However, it is also worth reflecting upon the value that can travel in the opposite direction; namely how these projects can benefit from the RDA, its activities and outputs. By being clear on this point, we can make the case that the RDA contributes to the development of the EOSC as well as its alignment with other commons around the globe.

5.1.1. Value contributed by the RDA TIGER Landscape Service

- a) The due diligence phases in projects are often time-sensitive, be it before a kick-off event or before making decisions between alternative approaches in order to meet milestone or deliverable schedules. Joining and engaging with an RDA WG and soliciting feedback from the group members can help focus the project contributions to areas where the impact is the highest (typically, gaps in the current state of the art). Seeking RDA TIGER help in identifying stakeholders that would have similar interests or partial solutions can allow further refinement of the search area.
- b) Identifying stakeholders that should be interested in project results will support the project's dissemination, engagement and exploitation plans. Especially parties the landscape analysis service contacts on behalf of the working group should be receptive to communications related to project progress.
- c) An independent landscape analysis supported by the community recommendations of the RDA Group are very valuable in situations where maximising the project's impact would require a contract amendment. Supporting material produced by a group of independent experts should reduce the amendment overhead for all parties involved.

5.1.2. Value contributed by RDA TIGER or connection with the RDA in general

- A) The impact of project deliverables has the potential to increase dramatically if they are included as reference material or direct contributions to RDA outputs. This automatically makes the project outputs part of the body of knowledge shared by the global community of FAIR data professionals.
- B) If these contributions are made in the context of an RDA TIGER-supported WG, the impact may be more immediate and will benefit from additional support measures such as external experts providing additional support for validation or proof-of-concept work; and communication support increasing the visibility of the outputs, to provide two examples.
- C) Once the Maintenance Platform is in production, authorship information and role as a background document will be visible on the RDA Knowledge Graph. This will increase the findability of the results among the target audience members (developers, data stewards, policymakers) considerably. In fact, one could argue that - due to the community-driven nature of the Maintenance Platform - the increased visibility is higher than what could be accomplished through search engine optimisation or a generous online advertisement budget.

- D) Joining RDA events and actively contributing to sessions (either as a participant or as an organiser) will increase the chances of fortuitous encounters. The transdisciplinary, global nature of RDA events makes them an ideal cross-pollination platform where solutions and approaches developed can find use cases outside their initial developer community, geographical area or application domain.

5.2. Growth and coverage of RDA WGs

In D3.1, published in June 2023, we found that there were 47 current RDA WGs. Thirty of these (63.8%) were dealing with cross-domain Open Science issues. At the time of writing this report, there are now 59 listed Working Groups (25 of which are currently in maintenance mode), and a further seven are not yet endorsed¹⁰⁶. Of this group of 59, there are 32 (54.2%) that appear to be dealing with domain-agnostic issues (and one further group on a multi-domain issue, which could also be considered as having a domain-agnostic outcome, albeit one currently being investigated within a range of domain-specific case studies)¹⁰⁷. Assuming the accuracy of these figures, this minor but noticeable shift to an increased proportion of WGs with domain specialisation is probably good news for the RDA in general, as it suggests an increase in diversity of research domains engaging with the RDA community in order to get deep work done. Meanwhile, as domain-agnostic WGs nonetheless slightly increase the strength of their number, if not their overall proportion of all groups, the important business of domain-agnostic and cross-domain group work continues to be one of the unique strengths of the RDA community.

The new set of *domain-agnostic* RDA working groups to date continue a strong tradition of activity around repositories particularly around the notion of operating as a trusted and trustworthy service. Part of this is the continued emphasis on (meta)data standards and on alignment and harmonisation of approaches to mappings and controlled vocabularies. Other growing areas of activity are the understanding of the landscape of existing tools and infrastructure, and expanded interaction with new tools such as uncrewed/unstaffed systems including drones and autonomous platforms, potentially corresponding with recent work on the use of (unstaffed) camera traps in biodiversity (WorldFAIR case study 9) and agricultural biodiversity (relevant to WorldFAIR case study 10, potentially the ‘agri-food’ theme of FAIR-IMPACT support, and the RDA Community of Practice ‘Improving Global Agricultural Data (IGAD)’).

In searching for trends within the new crop of *domain-specific* RDA working groups supported by TIGER, there is a clear theme around health and genomes, and another theme around agriculture and the environment. Data ethics appear amongst the new RDA working groups (including groups with specific focus on ethics in agricultural data and in health data) as well as the CODATA Data Ethics Task Group and the CODATA Data Integrity Working Group. The rise of AI and increased interest in ethical issues such as indigenous data rights

¹⁰⁶ https://www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_paged=6&_sort=date_desc

¹⁰⁷ As with D3.1, it is worth noting here that the source of knowledge for the most current up to date list of RDA WGs is via the RDA website: we are mindful that this list may not always be up-to-date, but we use it as the best reference point available.

and data colonialism may be reflected in the increasing, and welcome, prominence of ethics-related groups in the Open Science landscape.

5.3. Coverage of EOSC SRIA

The current crop of working groups supported by the RDA TIGER project are mapped against the latest version of the EOSC SRIA in section 1.1 above. We note that the current WG cohort corresponds to four of the seven current Implementation Challenges identified by the SRIA. Therefore, three of the current Implementation Challenges remain, namely: i) Authentication and authorisation infrastructure; ii) User Environments; and iii) Resource Provider Environments. This suggests a timely opportunity for encouragement of work in groups to respond to these three key challenge areas.

5.4. Geographical coverage

The Open Science landscape covered by this report is heavily skewed towards European and North American initiatives. This is partly due to the fact that we are working in English which predominates in scientific work in these regions. Notable omissions from the global landscape given here are the wealth of activity from the Spanish-speaking world; Chinese-language activities; and Francophone initiatives (other than the well-established and long-running RDA France initiative).

But when considering the most notable trend from the RDA WGs surveyed here, we see that a long-running issue still has not been resolved: from the WGs discussed here, where co-chair location is known, the distribution is as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of co-chairs per global region.

Co-chair location	Number of occurrences
Africa	2
Australasia	13
Europe	27
Central and South Americas	2
North America	15

As can be clearly seen, there is an obvious deficit in co-chairs based in Africa and in Central and South America, across the most recent RDA WGs. RDA has recently implemented requirements for a more equal distribution of co-chair origins. It is clear there remains a strong need for these requirements alongside a strengthening of effort via regions-based activities to improve co-chair recruitment from Africa and from the Central and South America regions. Representation of knowledge and experience across regions supports alignment and harmonisation of effort and practices globally, ensuring that local and regional initiatives (including e.g. EOSC) align with global developments and that we move towards an aligned, global Open Science system.

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